

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

CHARTER COMMUNICATION PLAN (UPDATED)

CHARTER Deliverable D7.19

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 54 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Authors: CHARTER coordination team / LAY

Co-funded by the participating European Facility of the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

CHARTER COMMUNICATION PLAN (UPDATED)

Version 1.0

CHARTER Deliverable 7.19

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 48 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Author(s): CHARTER coordination team / LAY

Due Submission Date: 30/09/2023

Actual Submission Date: 29/09/2023

Status	
Draft	
Final	x

Type		
R	Document, report	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER		

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission services)	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

Revision history

Date	Lead author(s)	Comments
20.08.2023	Markku Heikkilä	1 st draft version
25.8.2023	Sirpa Rasmus and Philip Burgess	2 nd draft version
29.8.2023	CHARTER coordination team	Final version, submitted

Table of Contents

Introduction	4
1. Internal communication.....	5
1.1.Email lists	5
1.2 Sharing and storing documents – Eduuni	6
1.3 Internal discussion forums and CHARTER webpage	6
1.4.Management structures and information flow	7
2. External communication to wide audience.....	8
3. Outreach tools and materials	11
4. External communication to selected target groups and stakeholders.....	12
4.1 EU Polar Cluster	12
4.2 Science centre	13
4.3.Policy briefs, working papers, factsheets	14
5. Monitoring communication and visibility	15
6. Schedule	16
MATERIAL AND LINKS	17

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

Introduction

Being a large international project, CHARTER also has a large number of communication target groups, audiences and methods. The main communication needs include:

1. Internal project communication
2. External communication to wide audience
3. Outreach tools and materials
4. External communication to selected target groups and stakeholders
5. Monitoring communication and visibility

CHARTER communication will ensure visibility of the project. The aim is to create awareness of questions related to the project among the general public, stakeholders/end users like local Arctic communities, decision-makers and the scientific community. Communication activities support CHARTER cross-cutting themes “Tools and data for Arctic Strategies”, and “Public dialogue on the Arctic”.

The project is coordinated from the Arctic Centre, University of Lapland, and thus the science communication unit of the Arctic Centre with the project managing team coordinates CHARTER overall communication.

Given the special character of CHARTER, the target groups for communication range from high-level EU and national officials and media, to remote Arctic communities. With this diversity of target groups in mind, the project needs to use a variety of communication methods. The project works with local people that have the right to know what this research is doing and why. Thus, communication starts from using understandable language in each level.

To serve this purpose, an easily understandable summary of the project aims is available on the website as a downloadable and printable pdf with versions in key languages of the project contacts, such as Finnish, North Sami, Inari Sami, Swedish, Russian, Nenets, English, French, German and even Bulgarian.

Dissemination, exploitation and communication are very tightly interconnected in CHARTER, and activities related to these will be carried out both by researcher and science communication experts in different partner institutes. Especially significant is the collaborative effort of WPs 6 and 7 in disseminating and communicating the results of the project.

Activities in WP6 (developing policy options, stakeholder dialogue) are not communication activities as such but the target groups and audiences may in many cases be similar. Therefore, good project internal cooperation is needed to identify

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

specific communication needs and opportunities in all work packages. As dissemination activities of WP6 take the form of participatory workshops, integrating the representatives of local communities into the research process and policy dialogue, WP7 concentrates on communicating the results to target audiences and coordinating the exploitation activities of CHARTER.

The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR plan) of CHARTER concentrates on exploitation and dissemination aspects, metrics to follow the project impact, the protection of project results (including Intellectual Property Rights), and innovative management.

1. Internal communication

One of the responsibilities of the project coordinator at the University of Lapland is to communicate with CHARTER partners and to coordinate the exchange of knowledge between them. The CHARTER partners form a large and diverse consortium. CHARTER diversity ranges from disciplines and research approaches to languages, nationalities, ethnicities, genders and career stages. This means that internal communication tools need to be developed and efficiently used to foster discussion, getting to know each other, and develop common understanding on terminology and concepts.

1.1. Email lists

CHARTER has email lists / list servers made and updated as needed:

- [CHARTER legal signatories@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_legal_signatories@ulapland.fi) (partner legal signatories)
- [CHARTER financial signatories@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_financial_signatories@ulapland.fi) (partner financial signatories)
- [CHARTER EC Portal@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_EC_Portal@ulapland.fi) (everyone listed in the EC portal)
- [CHARTER contact points@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_contact_points@ulapland.fi) (partner contact points)
- [CHARTER steering committee@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_steering_committee@ulapland.fi) (Steering Committee members)
- [CHARTER researchers@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_researchers@ulapland.fi) (all researchers involved)

WPs have email lists for their internal communication. WP-leaders can be contacted using their personal email addresses, or using a list server: [CHARTER WP-leaders@ulapland.fi](mailto:CHARTER_WP-leaders@ulapland.fi).

University of Lapland emails have the form firstname.familyname@ulapland.fi.

The Expert Advisory Group (EAG) can be contacted through the chair of the group, Markku Heikkilä.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

The contact information for certain roles (e.g. financial signatories) are found also in the EC portal. The mail lists (especially the CHARTER_researchers list) can be used not only by the project coordinators, but also by researchers when needed – for example, when cross-WP meetings need to be organized or information on upcoming events needs to be shared.

1.2 Sharing and storing documents – Eduuni

CHARTER uses shared University of Lapland Eduuni space to store and share documents. Eduuni can be used as a storage space, providing that the data is not sensitive¹, in that case it must be stored into external hard drives.

Users need to sign up with their email address to use the Eduuni services:

<https://id.eduuni.fi/signup/?lang=en>

Groups with certain access rights have been formed (for CHARTER researchers, collaborators and coordinators). People on CHARTER_researchers mail list have access to most of the CHARTER folders in Eduuni. Arctic Centre data specialist Arto Vitikka can help if there are technical problems.

Junior scientists have opened a Teams space and some WPs have opened Teams/Slack/some other spaces for their work. The project encourages researchers to use the tools found most flexible and useful.

The space in Eduuni is limited, so sharing and storing large files will be organized using other tools. Data management is an important part of storing and sharing material; this is covered in the Data Management Plan of CHARTER.

1.3 Internal discussion forums and CHARTER webpage

The space and time for CHARTER-wide discussion will be developed according to the needs and ideas from everyone participating. Virtual meeting tools (mainly Teams and Zoom) will be actively used.

Three shared documents have been opened to foster discussions and to follow CHARTER activities:

- Defining common terminology and discussing concepts
- What do the WPs need from each other?
- Following CHARTER activities (cross-WP work, outreach activities etc.)

¹ We define sensitive data as information comparable to patient health records, union membership or client relationship with social welfare; possible leak causes considerable damage to individuals.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

Junior scientists have organized bi-weekly networking meetings during the autumn 2020. Beginning from January 2021, regular CHARTER-wide meetings have been organized by LAY (Bruce Forbes, Sirpa Rasmus, Leena Leppänen, Teresa Komu). Some meetings will be more targeted to juniors, some will be thematic and for everyone to join. The idea of the meetings is to foster cross-disciplinary discussion and getting to know each other.

Cross-WP activities and discussions, organized by WPs and thematic working groups, are encouraged. The shared documents described above can be used to list what different WPs need from others, and to discuss concepts and terminology. The documents should also be used to follow the cross-WP activities that are planned and/or have taken place. This will help the reporting to the EC.

The CHARTER webpage is also a tool for internal communication. Some internal material has been put behind a password. Kick-off material and material from General Assemblies is stored there: minutes, notes, presentations and recordings, as well as the most important project documents (Management handbook, CHARTER work plan / description of action documents), EU and project logos, and Yamal maps discussed during the kick-off.

Links to the shared Google Docs can also be found there, as well as a link to CHARTER Eduuni and a link to the junior scientist network Google Docs.

About the webpages, contact Philip Burgess or Sirpa Rasmus.

1.4. Management structures and information flow

Internal project management practices, including the decision-making bodies and their meeting schedules, are described in the Management Handbook. The Handbook is found in CHARTER Eduuni and in the internal section of the webpage.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

2. External communication to wide audience

CHARTER external communication activities are to be carried out according to the general guidelines of WP7. The Science Communication unit of Arctic Centre at the University of Lapland plans and coordinates the communication activities, in close cooperation with the CHARTER Project Coordination team.

CHARTER has its own logo, visual image and templates. These were developed together with the website and are available for partners in the internal section of the website.

The CHARTER website <http://www.charter-arctic.org> is the main tool for continuous project visibility and project information. The website is updated actively throughout the project by the Project Coordination team.

CHARTER's twitter account @CharterArctic was created at the start of the project. The account is operated by the Project coordination team at the Arctic Centre. Retweets by Arctic Centre and other project partners are planned to enhance and facilitate spread of the messages. For example, Arctic Centre has over 9 000 followers. The partners will use the #CHARTERArctic hashtag when tweeting about their own project related activities.

However, Twitter (currently "X") internal development has dramatically reduced its usability as a credible tool for serious academic communication. While the CHARTER account still exists, the intensity in project use will be much reduced.

Other social media channels are not seen as necessary to be operated by the project. When it comes to Facebook, partner institutions are advised to use their own accounts. In this, Arctic Centre Facebook is the main channel. The project also aims to utilize Facebook pages and groups of project collaborators when possible; this way the message goes to targeted groups using a local language. In general, Facebook is also becoming a more problematic platform for academic outreach. One has to pay to get better visibility and some content definitions can be problematic. CHARTER does not run an Instagram account as it produces very little content that would work in Instagram in a meaningful way.

When it comes to YouTube, the CHARTER project maintains a specific playlist on the Arctic Centre YouTube channel and, when necessary and possible, those of the partner institutes.

All in all, while project such as CHARTER are encouraged to increase their visibility and reach in social media, the current developments in social media are not helping that goal and CHARTER's role there is to remain limited.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

All project-wide media releases are planned and coordinated by the Science Communication unit at Arctic Centre, after consulting with the project coordination team. All project partners are expected to name a communication contact person who can take care of modifying (also translating if necessary) the press releases to their respective institutional websites and sending them to media in channels they use. This will create a network of CHARTER communication contact points. Many CHARTER partner institutes have communication professionals who can support the communication activities of CHARTER by modifying and distributing press releases and other related material; for instance, communication department of UOXF, Helmholtz Climate Initiative / Climate Office for Polar Regions and Sea Level Rise at AWI, the communication department of UmU, and the Fram Centre in Norway.

It is also a fact that many partner universities and institutions can have much better access to the international media in their institutional communication than the Arctic Centre which is a rather small institution with limited reach to the research news distribution channels.

The project works actively with media, both through formal media releases and through smaller-scale or informal contacts.

Formal project-wide media releases include:

- project confirmation and first announcement
- selected main events and activities, themes to be decided during the project
- project end and main results

However, most of the ongoing media contacts are not pushed through all of the project institutions channels. For a project like CHARTER, field work and researchers' expertise offer many ways to work with different types of media: local, regional, national, international or thematically specialized media outlets. The options vary from citizen science events organized by the project to local workshops and thematic expert interviews. Project key words such as snow, ice, climate and reindeer offer many possibilities to showcase the project in interested media. Every year the Arctic Centre has numerous requests for expert interviews and when thematically relevant, they can be directed to CHARTER experts. Also, targeted media contacts will be utilized when for instance the project works visibly with local people.

Many activities take place in Lapland, Finland, as the project is coordinated there. The Finnish language media releases are visible on the Arctic Centre Finnish language website, which is an established source. It cannot be expected that local audience would follow CHARTER's English language site.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

WP leaders and other project actors are also encouraged to engage actively with local and regional media by informing them about local events and activities, giving interviews and writing background articles. WP leaders are responsible to oversee communication needs and activities that relate to specific WP actions such as workshops and discussion events. All WPs are expected to name a communications contact person. Communicating the scientific results is coordinated by WP6 and WP7.

CHARTER researchers will also participate in targeted journalist training with partners such as Finnish Association of Science Journalists and Finnish Association of Environment Journalists.

Apart from traditional press releases, other communication activities are carried out throughout the project. CHARTER WPs have a wide geographical and thematic scope and planned project activities include a number of local events and stakeholder contacts. Often these are also relevant for local media.

COVID-19 pandemic disrupted project activities in many unforeseen ways. Communication activities needed to be modified to fit the activities that CHARTER is actually able to carry out during the pandemic.

The project language is English even though English is not the language of any country belonging to key geographical scope of CHARTER (North-West Russia, Northern Fennoscandia). Therefore, in order to succeed, the project has to be able to communicate with the languages that people actually speak in the region, for instance by giving interviews in local languages and not in English when possible. A printable and downloadable summary of the project aims is available on the website with versions in key languages of the project contacts, such as Finnish, North Sami, Inari Sami, Swedish, Russian, Nenets, English, French, German and Bulgarian.

Communications units of the project partners bring the results available in their own context, thus adjusting them to their own media reality.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

3. Outreach tools and materials

The CHARTER website is of crucial importance in communicating the project idea and results. Therefore, the project has put special emphasis in developing the www.charter-arctic.org site to give a coherent and understandable picture of the project.

The website operates in English. Basic information of CHARTER is made available also in Finnish, Swedish, Sami, Russian and German with an option of other languages such as Nenets, in a format that is easy to print and distribute as a factsheet with key messages.

The website also has video interviews of WP leaders and selected researchers, videos and photos that help illustrate the project's aims and activities. Project partners are contributing to web contents, thus increasing the diversity of the site. Lack of physical meetings during the pandemic underlined the need for a well- functioning and comprehensible web content.

The website is structured so that all products of the project are easy to find. Publications is one of the main banners and under publications one can find newsletters, backgrounders, working papers (by WP 6), scientific publications, deliverables and media coverage.

Project news are available under the News banner. The news features project events, publications, researcher interviews and other updates, many of them also collected in the newsletters. Video gallery banner contains a number of researcher interviews, each one telling about their work in video interview format. CHARTER web contents follow the guidance of the EU Accessibility Directive and a GDPR requirements.

Project partners and personnel include individuals with visualization and science communication skills. This will be utilized in website content and other outreach activities. A number of possible outreach activities were highlighted in the project kick-off meeting and the project will encourage developing them further, within budgetary and personnel capacity limits.

Ideas on outreach as well as examples of tools and material were shared during the CHARTER kick-off meeting. These are found in the kick-off minutes and saved chat discussions, all found in the internal section of the webpage.

The project management team provides general guidelines such as short written project introductions, templates and general PowerPoint presentations, all according to EU visibility rules for a Horizon project. Project partners can use this material

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

when building their own communication and outreach activities.

The EC document “Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants” is aimed at assisting beneficiaries and gives relevant guidance for all CHARTER partners (see section “Material” below, and especially section “Sources and resources” in the document).

A CHARTER project newsletter is seen as a useful tool for internal and external communication with summaries of key recent developments and project news. The newsletter is published twice a year, with the first issue out after the autumn 2021 General Assembly. The newsletter can be subscribed to from the website.

A printed brochure or other material was not seen as relevant with the project start shadowed by the pandemic and lack of any physical meetings but if special needs arise during the remainder of the project, related communication hand-out materials will be and have been produced as required. The project also identifies existing outreach tools such as established websites or newsletters that could be used to help the project.

Besides templates and roll-ups, other physical CHARTER outreach materials will be limited. Some small materials such as stickers will be used but the project will not have pens, notebooks or similar small promotion material, in with sustainable development thinking. As physical meetings are becoming more frequent, the need for project posters and roll-ups will be considered case by case.

4. External communication to selected target groups and stakeholders

4.1 EU Polar Cluster

CHARTER has joined the EU Polar Cluster, a collaboration of Arctic and Antarctic projects funded by the European Commission. The benefits, as listed below at the EU Polar Cluster website, relate very much to project communication and visibility:

- Higher impacts than single project's outputs
- Upscale collective projects' efforts
- Increased knowledge sharing
- Less but better engagement with stakeholders
- Greater visibility
- Better use of citizen's money

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

Joining the EU Polar Cluster brings a direct way to access relevant EU communication channels and wider Arctic research communication channels. EU Polar Cluster utilizes Horizon Results Booster action that will help to strengthen the capacity of the cluster as a whole in disseminating and exploiting our research results. Cluster partners including CHARTER will be trained on how to disseminate the projects outcomes professionally towards e.g. decision-makers or other stakeholders. The cluster also has a number of common communication and visibility actions that can benefit CHARTER. The contact point for EU Polar Cluster communication activities is the Arctic Centre's communications specialist.

Projects in EU Polar Cluster tend to be natural science oriented. In contrast, CHARTER has a wider variety of approaches and much emphasis on people living in the Arctic. From the communication point of view, this gives CHARTER a chance to have a different and easily recognizable profile from most of the projects in the cluster.

4.2 Science centre

Arctic Centre operates the Arktikum Science Centre, the only Arctic science centre in Finland and in this scale, the only in the EU. During recent years, the exhibition has been visited by 110 000 – 130 000 visitors annually, about half of them from countries other than Finland. COVID 19 pandemic dramatically reduced the number of visitors.

The role of the Science Centre is to support the research consortium in tasks related to outreach and communication towards the general public and towards the local population concerned by the project outcome. The goal is to design and create a relevant communication tool to:

- promote the project relevance and progress to the general public;
- demonstrate the local and global meaningfulness of the project outputs to the population of concern;
- make the main results understandable for non-scientific audiences.

In order to reach these goals, the Science Centre will design and produce an interactive interface as the main communication tool towards the general public and local population. The interface will be integrated into an exhibition station into the permanent exhibition of the Arctic Centre. It will also be distributed into various electronic formats so that it can be displayed on several medias (phone, computers, tablets, etc.) in order to reach a maximum of audiences. The interface is easily portable even to our study regions.

The interface will include information related to the project as well as its main outcomes. The work is under the responsibility of the science communicator,

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

supported by the exhibition team and exhibition design service providers, who will gather the information, data and results via the researchers as well by participating in the fieldwork and workshops related activities. In the second phase, the science communicator will script the interface content in a popularized manner and start seeking assistance from exhibition design service providers to develop the most relevant interface for the content. In a final phase, the interface will be produced together by the exhibition team and the service provider. The expected result is an interactive and aesthetic interface introducing the main idea and outcomes of the project in a pedagogical manner contributing to raise understanding and the interest of the general public.

However, the original content plans need to be adjusted to the new reality and restrictions when it comes to field work and visits to the sites. This will be evaluated and decided during the first year of the project.

As part of the outreach and information efforts of the CHARTER project the development of an exhibit derived from aspects of the project scientific work has been underway and is planned to be installed by November, 2023. The exhibit focusses on the theme of the impacts of 'rain on snow', how warmer and wetter winters in the Arctic will impact plants, animals and people. The exhibit has three components that focus on human impact, research activities and snowpack animations. The Science Centre is visited by over 100,000 people per year.

4.3. Policy briefs, working papers, factsheets

A CHARTER working papers series has been established by WP6. By having the working papers visible and available publicly on the website under Publications, they also represent communication and outreach tools. These documents can be in any language relevant for CHARTER, and include policy briefs, reports, discussion pieces and background papers. Information about them will be sent by Twitter (X) and, when relevant, with press releases.

Partners are advised to utilize their communication departments to attain visibility for their results, activities and publications.

CHARTER provides content for related outreach material provided by the EU Polar Cluster.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

4.4. Project cooperation and conferences

Inside the EU Polar Cluster, CHARTER has identified “sister projects” among other Horizon2020 projects, such as ArcticHubs, JustNorth, ECOTIP and FACE-IT. Joint policy briefing events and joint participation in related conferences (such as Arctic Frontiers, Arctic Circle Assembly, Rovaniemi Arctic Spirit) enhances stakeholder access and visibility in Brussels as well as in the Arctic region.

In partnership with two other Horizon2020 funded projects (ECOTIP and FACE-IT), a policy briefing to EU policy makers was held in Brussels in early 2022. The event hosted up to 70 people from a variety of EU bodies. The event comprised of presentations by the three projects, a panel discussion and was followed by a presentation of posters and multimedia outputs in the ORBN building which houses the DG Research and Innovation. A collective policy briefing document was developed specifically for this event.

5. Monitoring communication and visibility

As a project, CHARTER is required to follow and report some dissemination and communication activities. The number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project for each of the following categories:

- Organisation of a Conference
- Organisation of a Workshop
- Press release
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)
- Exhibition
- Flyer
- Training
- Social Media
- Website
- Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop
- Video/Film
- Brokerage Event
- Pitch Event
- Trade Fair
- Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

We will also follow and report the estimated number of persons reached, in the by all dissemination and communication activities, in each of the following categories:

- Scientific Community (Higher education, Research)
- Industry
- Civil Society
- General Public
- Policy Makers
- Media
- Investors
- Customers
- Other

The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) lists metrics which help to follow the impact of the project and which are relevant for the exploitation through the cross-cutting themes “Tools and data for Arctic Strategies”, and “Public dialogue on the Arctic”.

6. Schedule

Communication is one item on the agenda for all CHARTER Steering Committee meetings, as well as for Project Management Group meetings.

Following table gives a preliminary schedule for communication activities:

<i>Communication activity</i>	<i>Project Month</i>
CHARTER logo and visual image	1
Website (ongoing)	1
Twitter (ongoing)	1
Newsletter (ongoing after first issue)	12
Video interviews with project researchers	2
Joining EU Polar Cluster Results Booster	3
Project communication contact group	5-6
CHARTER factsheet translations	3-6
Infographic of the main idea of and expected outcomes	12
Interactive interface developed	50
Communicating project results	when appropriate
Media releases (ongoing, attached to project activities) - -project end and main results	46-54

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869471

MATERIAL AND LINKS

CHARTER website: <http://www.charter-arctic.org>

CHARTER X (Twitter) account: @CharterArctic

Arctic Centre web page: www.arcticcentre.org

CHARTER YouTube playlist:

<https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6SojJRvu9GT>

[_AbAQ-HQONh5Bl8W1xTtK](https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL6SojJRvu9GT_AbAQ-HQONh5Bl8W1xTtK)

EU Accessibility Directive:

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/web-accessibility>

EC Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, H2020 Programme: Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects (Version 1.1, 07 January 2020)

EC H2020 Programme: Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants (Version 1.0, 25 September 2014)

EU Polar Cluster website: <https://www.polarcluster.eu/>